

EOM4SOIL

Report 6.3

Results from Focus groups on the EOMs value-chains in Italy

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1. Introduction

The present report aims at describing the bottom-up approach used to collect information on the sustainability of Exogenous Organic Matters (EOMs) value chains in Italy and the results achieved in the framework of the Task 6.2.3 Bottom-up dialogue at local level: case studies for a EOMs realistic evaluation. This work has the aim to support the development of useful guidelines for end-users (Subtask 6.1.2) and fair policies promoting the sustainable use of Exogenous Organic Matters (EOMs) (Subtask 6.2.2).

The bottom-up dialogue among actors of different EOMs value chains, in particular biochar, digestate, manure and compost has been established, in Italy, in spring 2024. More specifically, focus groups on biochar, digestate, manure and compost production and use have been conducted to gather more realistic knowledge of the EOMs value chains in specific local contexts and, more generally, at national level.

CREA researchers organized the live focus groups with the aim of collecting information about:

- gaps in legislation for EOMs producers and farmers;
- environmental sustainability of EOMs use in different contexts (e.g. where relevant: Nitrate Vulnerable Zones - NVZ vs. non-Nitrate Vulnerable Zones – nNVZ, as defined by the European Directive 91/676/CEE);
- economic sustainability for EOMs producers and farmers (needs and barriers).

A couple of examples can highlight the diversity of EOMs value chains in Italy and the importance of the local context on EOMs availability and use, supporting the idea of developing specific focus groups per EOM and area:

1. the Italian Northern Regions can be described as a case study, where common strengths and problems connected with the production and use of digestate are present. In fact, in these Regions biogas plants are highly concentrated (83,4% of the 2.201 biogas plants in Italy in 2021), with a consequent high production (the majority of the 3 million tonnes per year produced in Italy) and application of digestate. However, application rates are limited by the European Directive 91/676/CEE for Nitrate Vulnerable Zones (NVZs) vs. non-Nitrate Vulnerable Zones (nNVZs).
2. biochar value chain is still very poorly developed in Italy. Out of the 29 authorized biochar producers in Italy, only 6 are currently producing biochar (around 1000 t/year) because of strict regulations on physicochemical characteristics of the biochar, economic unsustainability of the production plants and no demand by farmers.

2. Focus groups methodology

The focus groups were opened to a maximum of 30 invited participants, to facilitate interaction, representing each phase of the value chain. The actors that participated to the focus groups were highly relevant: Ministry of Agriculture, Regional authorities, Environmental quality inspectors, research institutes, EOMs producers and producers' associations, farmers, farmers' association, multinational enterprises, carbon credits certifiers, EOMs dealers and distributors.

Focus groups were conducted with the following structure:

- introductory session about the EOM4SOIL project goals and findings;
- introduction to the goals of the focus group and the state of the art about the specific EOM production and use in Italy;
- introduction of participants (affiliation and role in the EOM value chain);
- division of participants into 4 working groups for discussion around tables. Each group was guided by a mentor to define the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats of EOM production and use. A rapporteur was chosen among the participants of each group;
- the rapporteur presented in a plenary session a summary of the discussion held in each of the table and the plenary debate was opened.

3. Results

3.1. Focus group on biochar

As stated in the introduction section, the biochar value chain is poorly developed in Italy, therefore we organized only one focus group on this EOM, because this was sufficient to gather most of the national actors in this field. Moreover, biochar application to the soil does not contribute to nitrate leaching, as it the case for digestate, therefore this criterion was not considered as a crucial aspect in the organization of the focus groups (NVZs vs. NNVZs).

The focus group was organized in Reggio Emilia, Northern Italy in the Tecnopolo, a location that was made available by the CRPA (Research Center on Animal Production) (Fig. 1) and it was organised in collaboration with AIEL (Italian Association of Agro-forestry energy) in the framework of the BioRural project (Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas, an HORIZON project). The collaboration with BioRural was strategic to share costs of the event organization and to guarantee a high participation to the event, given that the objective of the projects was similar as well as the timing and therefore it was important to avoid overlapping.

The participants to the focus group are reported in Tab. 1.

Fig. 1: Opening of the focus group on biochar held in Reggio Emilia (Italy) with the introduction of the EOM4SOIL project made by Maria Valentina Lasorella, responsible of the project for CREA-PB (on the left) and working groups around tables (on the right).

Name	Type of stakeholder
AICHIO20	carbon credits certifier
Alga Power	potential biochar producer and investor
Asja Ambiente Italia S.p.a.	potential biochar producer and investor
ARPA Lombardia	Regional Agency for Environmental Protection
BioDea Bio-Esperia S.r.l.	biochar and energy plants producer
Confagricoltura Mantova	farmers association
CNR	Research center
CRPA	research center
Evergreen resources S.r.l.	biochar and energy plants producer
Felsina S.p.a.	farmer using biochar in vineyards
Ferrero	potential biochar producer and investor
Frantoio di Greve Pesa	biochar producer and field application in vineyards and olive groves
Frescobaldi	biochar producer and field application in vineyards
ICHAR	Italian biochar association
IPAG	Fertilisers and biochar distributor
KiRa Technology s.r.l.	biochar and energy plants producer
MASAF	Italian ministry of agriculture, food and forests
Medenergy s.r.l.	biochar distributor
Nera Biochar s.r.l.	biochar and energy plants producer
Reato Energie	biochar and energy plants producer
Re-Cord	private-public nonprofit Research & Development organization
Regione Emilia Romagna	Regional administration (Sustainable agriculture department)
UNIMORE	University of Modena and Reggio Emilia
Yanmar	gasification plants developer

Tab. 1: Participants to the focus group about biochar value-chain in Italy. For some stakeholders, more than one person participated in the focus group.

The discussion in the working groups was facilitated by CREA and AIEL personnel and supported by the use of A0 size canvas, where the rapporteur could take notes summarising the discussion. The canvas was organized in several sections:

- Description of the currently more frequent energy, fertilizers and amendments production and use systems in Italy.
- Problems of the current system (linear economy system with biomass waste disposal, pollution, GHG emissions)
- Description of the biochar production and use system, including the renewable energy production associated with these EOMs.
- Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats of EOMs value chains in Italy or in the local context, where relevant
- Innovative ideas to solve the weaknesses of the value chains (Fig. 2).

In the following link it is possible to see a video regarding the focus group: <https://youtu.be/M0xe36-IIHI?si=AYp50UQ4pgUhTfJh>

Fig. 2: Canvas used to take notes summarising the discussion in the working groups around tables

3.1.1. Main outcomes of the focus group on biochar

The barriers of the Italian biochar value-chain highlighted in the discussion of tables are summarized in Tab. 2 together with possible solutions and innovations for the value-chain.

Issue	Possible solutions and innovations
Group A	
No economic viability of biochar production plants.	Production and exploitation of condensed co-products which have a better market in Italy, compared to biochar, to be used as bio-stimulants or pesticides.
Complexity, high costs of installation and maintenance of industrial plants	Promote and test a new technology available in Italy: 1 kWe plants.
Low biochar demand from the agricultural sector.	<p>Promote other uses of biochar in agriculture:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Animal feeding • animal bedding • filtering of air pollutants emissions from animal slurry (i.e., NH₄) • direct filtering of the liquid fraction of the slurry • input for digestate plants. <p>In all these cases, the biochar is enriched by nutrients, and therefore results to be a better fertiliser when applied to the soil.</p>
High investments needed for new gasification and pyrolysis plants not affordable by the single farm, especially if small scale.	<p>Biochar production in composting plants from organic and green waste.</p> <p>Inside a composting plant, the humid fraction of urban waste as well as the softer part of pruning residues (leaves and small branches) can be used for compost production. The hardest fraction of the pruning residues (branches), which are also classified as waste in Italy, could be used for biochar production in a pyrolysis or gasification plant located directly in the composting plant. The plant could be used for energy production and the biochar could be added to the compost to improve the agronomic and climate mitigation performances of the compost. The addition of biochar even in small percentages (1%) in the compost mounds have been shown to reduce the GHG emission of the process as well as to improve the thermal behaviour of the process. Attention must be given to the level of contaminants in the pruning residues (heavy metals and pesticides).</p> <p>Creation of “ecosystemic communities”</p> <p>Inspired by the example of energy communities, stakeholders propose to gather subjects that have waste biomass available, and do not know how to value it, into associations to use it for energy and biochar production in a shared pyrolysis or gasification plant. The biochar is then distributed to the association’s members.</p>
Group B	

<p>The size, complexity and costs of the industrial plants do not fit the needs of small Italian farms that want to recycle and value their pruning residues</p>	<p>Develop small pyrolysis plants with simple technology, that can be developed or bought at the small-scale farm level (self-produced or commercially available). Such plants can be used when pruning residues from the farm are available. A more flexible option would be the development of mobile pyrolysis plants.</p>
<p>Investment costs and complexity of maintenance, make gasification plants not affordable and manageable also for bigger farms.</p>	<p>Build farms consortium-level gasification plants that can be fed with the pruning residues collected by all consortium's partners, so that the plant can be used the whole year-round. Energy can be recovered, and biochar can be redistributed among the consortium's farms.</p>
<p>Low biochar use in agricultural and floricultural sectors.</p>	<p>Increase biochar awareness by training agronomists and advisors to reach more farmers.</p> <p>Increase biochar industrial production so that distributors and retailers can propose it to the farmers as a commercially available amendment.</p>
<p>Group C</p>	
<p>Feedstock availability is not constant during the year if this is deriving from pruning and most pyrolysis and gasification plant accept only specific types of biomasses</p>	<p>Create small-scale value chains. For instance, vine growers or olive growers can create a consortium, collect pruning residues, exploit them for energy production in a gasification plant built at the Consortium level, and then the biochar can be distributed to the Consortium partners.</p>
<p>High cost of plants even at consortium level</p>	<p>Need for incentives</p>
<p>Emissions due to the transportation of feedstock to the production unit. If input biomass is taken from a long distance, biochar production is not environmentally sustainable.</p>	<p>Local value chains, e.g. at Consortium level, or small-scale mobile production units transported to different farms when biomass is available for biochar production.</p>
<p>Biochar knowledge gap. The use of biochar in agriculture have been highly disseminated in Italy, even if not effectively enough. However, other usages of biochar are even less well-known. This is relevant especially for producers who are not able to respect the regulation limits about the usage in agriculture. At the moment, they are not well aware of alternative usages (composites, batteries, filters, cement...), respective legislation and existing value chains.</p>	<p>Define the characteristics of biochar when it is intended for other usages than the agricultural management.</p> <p>Promote dissemination about other usages of biochar, the currently existing value chains and regulation.</p> <p>If no dedicated regulation exists, it is necessary to define it.</p>
<p>Group D</p>	

<p>Knowledge gaps about biochar among experts (researchers, producers, distributors) and farmers.</p>	<p>More dissemination.</p>
<p>Economic sustainability: high costs of production and consequent high biochar's price. Farmers will be ready to pay such a high price only if biochar brings evident effects within a short time after application, but this is not always the case.</p>	<p>A possible contribution to the economic sustainability can come from carbon credits even if also this system is not very well established:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • low prices • very different certification options • high certification costs • low reliability of some certifications
<p>Biochar quality depends on the technology (pyrolysis vs. gasification) and on the feedstock used. Therefore, it is hard to sell biochar because farmers cannot always have access to the same product and therefore cannot predict its impact.</p>	<p>Market segmentation depending on the biochar characteristics.</p> <p>Promote high quality and highly efficient biochar in agriculture to firstly enter in the market and increase farmers' trust.</p>
<p>Need to increase awareness about low soil health in EU and the fact that biochar can have multiple positive effects on soil health, and not only climate change mitigation: e.g., water holding capacity, biochar can be a prevention therapy for water shortage.</p>	<p>Improve the communication around biochar.</p>

Tab. 2: Barriers and possible solutions for the Italian biochar value-chain

3.2. Focus group on digestate

The Italian supply chain of anaerobic digestion, that regards biogas, biomethane and digestate production and use, has been analysed in a focus group to understand its strengths and weaknesses and to propose possible innovative solutions for the latter. In fact, despite the considerable development and diffusion of digestate production and use, based on previous investigations, CREA was aware of the problems and the potentials of such a value chain in Italy (e.g., regionalized EOM production, reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) and pollutants emissions compared to chemical fertilizers use, respectively).

The focus group was organized in Rome, Central Italy, in the Biblioteca Storica Nigro, a location made available by CREA (Fig. 3) and was organized in collaboration with AIEL (Italian Association of Agro-forestry energy) as part of the BioRural project (Accelerating the circular integration of bio-based solutions in European rural areas, a HORIZON project). As for the focus group on biochar, the collaboration with BioRural was strategic to share the costs of organizing the event and to ensure high participation from stakeholders.

The participants attending the focus group are reported in Tab. 3.

Name	Type of stakeholder
CIA	Farmers association
Copagri	Farmers association
CIB	Farmers association
Coldiretti	Farmers association
Confagricoltura	Farmers association
ISPRA	Research center
ENEA	Research center
GSE	Research center
Foundation Farming for future	Agritech National Technology Transfer Center supported by CDP Venture Capital together with ToSeed Partners
University of the studies of Perugia	Scientific and technological university
POLIMI - Milan Polytechnic	Scientific and technological university
ITABIA	Italian Biomass Association
CTI	Italian Thermotechnical Committee
CRPA	Research center

Tab. 3: Participants to the focus group about digestate value-chain in Italy. For some stakeholders, more than one person participated to the focus group.

Fig. 3: Opening of the focus group on digestate held in Rome (Italy) with the introduction of the EOM4SOIL project made by Ilaria Falconi (CREA-PB) and working groups around tables.

As for the focus group on biochar, the discussion within the working groups was facilitated by CREA and AIEL staff and supported by the use of A0-sized canvases. For logistics reasons, some of the participants couldn't attend the meeting in person, therefore an online working group was organized and the topics emerging from the discussion were noted down on a digital document (Fig. 4).

The canvases were divided into the following sections:

- Description of the most common production and use systems in Italy.
- Problems of the current system of fertilizers and energy production and use (legislation, air pollution, GHG emissions, nitrogen leaching in watercourses, infrastructure, etc.)
- Description of the digestate production and use system, including the renewable energy production associated with such EOM.
- Strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of digestate value chain in Italy and in local contexts.
- Innovative ideas to solve the weaknesses of value chains (Fig. 4).

IDEE INNOVATIVE FILERA BIOGAS BIOMETANO - DIGESTATO

**CRITICITA' e SOLUZIONI
 FILERA BIOGAS BIOMETANO - DIGESTATO**

Fig. 4: Canvases used to take notes during the discussion in the working groups around tables (2 paper canvas for peoples in presence and 1 digital canvas for the online working group).

3.2.1. Main outcomes of the focus group on digestate

The barriers of the Italian digestate value-chain highlighted in the discussion of tables are summarized in Tab. 4, together with possible solutions and innovations.

Issue	Possible solutions and innovations
Group A	
Absence of integrated supply chains in the territories.	To encourage the development of integrated supply chains in reference territories to create renewable energy communities.
Absence of new technology and innovation for the development of the anaerobic digestion chain.	Supporting applied research that provides a response and support to agricultural entrepreneurs (EIP-AGRI) e.g., in the following sectors: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop innovative solutions for the recovery of biogenic CO₂ from the biogas/biomethane production process in order to use it in the chemical (green) sector. • Increase the fertiliser value of the digestate by combining various organic matrices (e.g. digestate + compost, digestate + algae, digestate + biochar).
Low value of digestate.	Increase the fertiliser value of digestate by combining various organic substances (e.g. digestate + compost, digestate + algae, digestate + biochar). For example, combining digestate with biochar would make digestate a more stable fertiliser in the soil.
Rare LCA evaluation of the value chain. Lack of models to estimate the benefits of the process.	Development of applications and software such as modular systems that can simulate both the emissions of the entire production and use cycle and the absorption of CO ₂ (important aspects for the carbon credits sector).
Group B	
The distribution of effluents and, consequently, of digestate is very regionalized (mainly in the Northern Italian regions characterized by the presence of vast NVZs).	Innovative solutions for the use of effluents and digestate (other than agronomic and energy use). Revision of nitrate legislation to comply with guidance from the Joint Research Centre (JRC) ¹ in the recently published report on technical proposals for the safe use of livestock manure above the threshold laid down for nitrate vulnerable zones by the Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC). It is necessary to ensure a reliable regulatory framework for the agronomic use of digestate.
For the agronomic use of digestate: 1. Disinformation among technicians and users (or agricultural enterprises). Indeed, poor knowledge and lack of application of	1. Encouraging farm advisory services by farm advisory bodies to train and inform farmers on farm standards and good agricultural practices.

¹ Huygens D, Orveillon G, Lugato E, Tavazzi S, Comero S, Jones A, Gawlik B, Saveyn HGM, Technical proposals for the safe use of processed manure above the threshold established for Nitrate Vulnerable Zones by the Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC), EUR 30363 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2020, ISBN 978-92-76-21539-4, doi:10.2760/373351, JRC121636

<p>digestate in the regions of Southern Italy in particular, in organic farms.</p> <p>2. The presence of an obsolete agricultural fleet and a rather slow generational turnover does not allow the implementation of innovation in agriculture and the application of sustainable management techniques, e.g., the application of organic matter to the soil.</p>	<p>2. Increase of funds for the purchase of agricultural machinery and equipment that allow precision agriculture, burial during the spreading of digestate or direct injection. These funds must also include the scrapping of agricultural machinery on the farm.</p>
<p>Lack of access to key data for environmental assessment (e.g. type and quantity of matrices entering the plant, quantity of product leaving the plant, etc.). The difficulty of sharing information between research institutions and administrations. The absence of a quality data (information on matrices entering the system aggregated, that is, there are only data on the substrate and not on individual organic matrices; data format, that is, some data are paper and others have been digitized). To date, the only accurate information is related to the production of renewable energy input and financial resources spent and planned for the implementation of the intervention.</p>	<p>Encourage collaboration between research institutions, professional organisations, universities and administrations in order to ensure both the sharing and the systemisation of data and to improve the quality of the information produced. It's important to get some disaggregated information about input matrices, representative of the peculiarities of the territory and having the same format in order to provide an analysis of the potential and benefits of anaerobic digestion.</p> <p>It would also be appropriate to incorporate the scientific information resulting from research projects and university studies.</p> <p>The interaction of administrative, energy, business, project, financial, input and output data is expected.</p> <p>Access to data will allow, finally, to analyze the cost of investment and the results produced in terms of development of the bioeconomy, employment, diversification of agricultural income, reduction of environmental impacts (GHG and ammonia emissions, eutrophication) and environmental benefits (improvement of air quality and water bodies, climate mitigation, soil protection).</p>
<p>Lack of a strategic vision. Inconsistency between policies: many policies, being sectoral, lose their effectiveness and/or contribute to confusion of interpretations or hierarchies of importance. Think of the overlap between land use for food production and climate mitigation (objectives of the green new deal and the European climate law) and the spread of renewable energy (objective of the European climate law and Repower UE).</p> <p>This inconsistency makes it difficult for farmers to organise (investments for the ecological transition of their farms).</p>	<p>National and European policies should be coordinated in order to ensure a strategic vision. There must be a link between policy, objective, research and the financial resources to be planned and allocated.</p>
<p>Lack of recognition of the role of agroenergies for the sector. No economic interventions aimed at supporting businesses and the supply chain. The incentives are linked to the activation/implementation of the biogas plant or its conversion to produce biomethane. The</p>	<p>It is necessary to recognise an economic value (quantify/monetize) to the ecosystem services provided by farms and the anaerobic digestion chain (e.g. climate mitigation of the sector, increase in organic matter on the ground, decarbonisation of other sectors) since the costs to be incurred for the management and production in anaerobic digestion systems are significantly higher than those of a photovoltaic system.</p>

economic revenue is linked exclusively to the energy production placed on the market.	
<p><u>For the use of biomethane:</u></p> <p>There is no rapid timetable for the connection to the gas network and the integration between the transmission and distribution networks.</p> <p>High cost for network access.</p> <p>Management of small biogas plants.</p>	It is necessary to ensure a rapid timetable for connection to the gas network and greater integration between the transmission and distribution networks. It would be desirable to safeguard the continuation of production both of biogas plants that cannot be converted to biomethane and for small plants.
Group C	
The old regulatory framework (e.g. Nitrates Directive) does not allow the development of digestate and the reduction of the use of chemical fertilizers in agriculture.	Updating and adaptation of legislation to ensure digestate equivalent and to make digestate a transportable product.
Disinformation of employees of public bodies (e.g. regional officials) involved in the management chain.	Encouraging the training of policymakers. Draw up guidelines on good practice in using digestate.
Low technological innovation and insufficient financial resources.	Programming and stabilisation of incentive instruments. Technological innovation aimed at using lignocellulosic residues in the anaerobic digestion plant.
Enhance the ecosystem services provided by the anaerobic digestion chain in the context, for example, of the European regulation on carbon farming.	Efforts should be made to include the agronomic use of digestate as one of the practices to generate carbon credits.

Tab. 4: Barriers and possible solutions for the Italian digestate value-chain.

3.3. Focus group on manure

In Italy, the management of livestock manure in all phases (shelter, storage and spreading) represents both the main emission category of GHG and ammonia in the agricultural sector and the main cause of eutrophication. During the focus group, participants analyzed the agricultural use of manure, different manure management techniques, its use in the anaerobic digestion process and innovative solutions for its management in the farm.

The focus group was organized by CREA (Council for Research in Agriculture and the analysis of the agricultural economy) in Reggio Emilia, Northern Italy in the Tecnopolo (Fig. 5) and was organized in collaboration with CRPA (Research Center on Animal Production) as part of the project “Pro Acque”, a project funded by the Rural Development Programme (EU and Emilia Romagna region) aiming at promoting a circular and sustainable management of livestock effluents to protect water quality. The participants to the focus group are reported in Tab. 5.

Fig. 5: Opening of the focus group on manure held in Reggio Emilia (Italy) with the introduction of the EOM4SOIL project made by Maria Valentina Lasorella (CREA-PB) and working groups around tables.

Name	Type of stakeholder
Coldiretti	Farmers association
Confagricoltura	Farmers association
AIEL	Italian Association of Agroforestry Energies
CRPA	Research center
UNIMORE - University of Modena and Reggio Emilia	Scientific and technological university
Livestock farm of the Modena Apennines	Farmer
CREA	Research center

Tab. 5: Participants to the focus group about manure value-chain in Italy. For some stakeholders, more than one person participated to the focus group.

Discussion within the working groups was facilitated by CREA and CRPA staff and supported by the use of A0-sized canvases.

The canvases were organized into the following sections:

- Description of the most common use systems in Italy.
- Problems of the current system (legislation, air pollution, GHG emissions, nitrogen leaching in watercourses, infrastructure, etc.).
- Description of the manure use system, including the renewable energy production associated with such EOM.
- Strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of manure value chain in Italy or in local contexts.
- Innovative ideas to solve the weaknesses of the value chain (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6: Canvases used to take notes during the discussion in the working groups around tables.

3.3.1. Main outcomes of the focus group on manure

The barriers of the Italian manure value-chain highlighted in the discussion of tables are summarized in Tab. 6, together with possible solutions and innovations.

Issue	Possible solutions and innovations
Group A	
<p>The distribution of effluents is very regionalized (mainly in the Northern Italian regions characterized by the presence of vast NVZs).</p> <p>Discrepancy between the regulatory framework (Nitrates Directive) and the evolution of climatic conditions (e.g. the period of the spreading bans provided for by Italian Regulation DM n. 5046 of 2016 transposing the Nitrate Directive).</p>	<p>Innovative solutions for the use of effluents, other than agronomic and energy use, such as the bioplastic production (see paragraph on “Low value of manure” in this table).</p> <p>Revision of nitrate legislation to comply with guidance from the Joint Research Centre (JRC) in the recently published report on technical proposals for the safe use of livestock manure above the threshold laid down for nitrate vulnerable zones by the Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC).</p> <p>Lay down rules on manure spreading which are harmonised with the crop plan and the climatic conditions.</p>
<p>The presence of an obsolete agricultural machinery fleet and a rather slow generational turnover does not allow the implementation of innovation in agriculture and the application of sustainable management techniques, e.g., manure burial during spreading, direct injection and fertigation</p>	<p>Increase of funds for the purchase of agricultural machinery and equipment that allow precision agriculture, burial during the spreading of manure or direct injection. These funds must also include the scrapping of farms’ agricultural machinery.</p>
<p>Low value of manure.</p>	<p>Encouraging the innovative uses of manure (e.g. the use of poultry manure combined with pruning cuttings for the production of organic fertilizers and bioplastic films to be used in mulching and/or for the realization of pots in horticulture, thanks to the action of the black soldier fly, <i>Hermetia illucens</i>)².</p>
<p>Poor transfer of technological innovation. Disconnection between research findings and farm activities.</p>	<p>Encouraging farm advisory services by farm advisory bodies to train and inform farmers on good agricultural practices. Increase field testing on farms.</p> <p>Promote and activate a 360° farm advisory service, not primarily aimed at the sale of commercial products for farm management but to promote the knowledge of sustainable techniques and training activities based on farms’ peculiarities.</p>
<p>Poor application of innovative/experimental manure management techniques to reduce environmental impacts.</p>	<p>To promote on-farm experimentation to encourage the use of manure management techniques able to reduce GHG and ammonia emissions such as the production of struvite,</p>

² Setti, L.; Francia, E.; Pulvirenti, A.; De Leo, R.; Martinelli, S.; Maistrello, L.; Macavei, L.I.; Montorsi, M.; Barbi, S.; Ronga, D. Bioplastic Film from Black Soldier Fly Prepupae Proteins Used as Mulch: Preliminary Results. *Agronomy* **2020**, *10*, 933. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy10070933>

	slow-release, prototypal and stable fertilizers recovered from digestate or effluents, and the use of additives in effluent storage tanks.
Poor organisation of the manure management value-chain.	<p>The service should be structured to ensure the aggregation of materials (e.g. manure) and/or agricultural holdings. It is suggested to manage the manure at a consortium level in order to enhance its valorisation (e.g., soil amendment, biogas and biomethane production). Simplifications should therefore be ensured, at the bureaucratic level, to manage manure among farms located in the surroundings of manure's storage locations (e.g., Schiavon plant, in Veneto, Northern Italy, video reportage under editing).</p> <p>This management would allow companies to cooperate and manage in an associated manner the organic matrix, the agricultural machinery, biogas plants, etc.</p> <p>Finally, the management of manure and the organization of the supply chain should be sewn on the characteristics of the farm to improve manure use for various purposes (e.g. mix with other EOMs, energy production, heat or bioproducts).</p>
Innovations and dedicated resources only for large anaerobic digestion plants and biomethane production (biogas is less supported).	<p>Adequate resources should be provided to support small anaerobic digestion plants that cannot be converted to the production of biomethane, and to ensure the technological innovation of such plants (e.g. storage of ammonia).</p> <p>Depending on the size of the anaerobic digestion plant, multiple solutions (digestate, biogas, biomethane, ammonia storage, input EOM mix, etc.) should be supported.</p>
Group B	
Manure management problems on the farm (e.g. spreading considering the Nitrates Directive and interaction between effluent heaps and wildlife).	To increase farm advice in order to ensure the application of sustainable and efficient manure management techniques such as, for example, the contextual management of manure collection and spreading, precision farming, the application of suitable manure spreading techniques).
Little combination of various EOMs such as, for example, manure and compost.	Ensure the use of digestate in combination with good-quality compost by implementing practices to prevent the presence in the anaerobic digestion plant of impurities (e.g. plastic or bioplastic present in the compost. It should be noted that the bioplastic degrades in time periods exceeding the 60 days required to produce the compost).
No or low economic value of manure.	Monetize the ecosystem services provided by the sustainable application of manure to soil or its delivery to an anaerobic digestion plant. Ensure an appropriate reward for farmers based on the virtuous path adopted by the

	agricultural enterprise (e.g. application and combination of agri-climate and environmental measures).
The old regulatory framework (e.g. Nitrates Directive) does not allow the development of manure and digestate production and use value-chain and the reduction of the use of chemical fertilizers in agriculture.	Update and adaptation of legislation. The legislation should adapt to innovative organic matter management technologies.

Tab. 6: Barriers and possible solution for the Italian manure value-chain.

3.4. Focus group on compost

In Italy, the revision of the legislation on waste management, related to the transposition of the provisions provided for by the "Circular Economy Package"³ in Legislative Decree no. 152/2006, has diversified the plant material used to produce compost. Urban green mowing is classified as waste, while mowing and pruning obtained from good farming practice is subject to the provisions of article 185, comma 1, letter f) of the Legislative Decree no. 152/2006 and, therefore, are excluded from the regulatory scope of waste. In Italy, most of the compost produced comes from municipal waste (cuttings produced by the maintenance of urban green areas). In detail, about 7.5 million tons of cuttings from the maintenance of the urban green areas are used to produce about 1.9 million tons.

During the focus group, participants analyzed the agricultural use of compost, origin and its possible management techniques, barriers to the development of the supply chain and its use for the promotion of innovative solutions. In addition, during focus group have been considered urban waste and public greenery, corresponding to an annual quantity of approximately 7.3 million tonnes, made up of organic waste (5.5 million tonnes) and greenery (1.8 million of tons); if sewage sludge and agro-industry waste are also taken into consideration, the figure reaches 8.4 million tonnes. This quantity is transformed into approximately 1.9 million tonnes of compost, including mixed composted soil improver, green composted soil improver and composted soil improver with sludge, as well as 409 million cubic meters of biogas and 167 million cubic meters of biomethane (CIC, 2024)

The focus group was organized by CREA in Reggio Emilia, Northern Italy in the Tecnopolo (Fig. 7) and was organized in collaboration with CRPA as part of the project "Pro Acque". The participants to the focus group are reported in Tab. 7.

³ [Directive \(EU\) 2018/851 of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Directive 2008/98/EC on waste.](https://www.fao.org/faolex/results/details/en/c/LEX-FAOC178599/)

Fig. 7: Opening of the focus group on compost held in Reggio Emilia (Italy) with the introduction of the EOM4SOIL project made by Valentina Lasorella (CREA-PB) and working groups around tables.

Name	Type of stakeholder
CREA	Research center
CRPA	Research center
CIC - Consorzio Italiano Compostatori	Trade organisation
ENOMONDO - Caviro Group	Production plants

Tab. 7 Participants to the focus group about compost value-chain in Italy. For some stakeholders, more than one person participated to the focus group.

Discussion within the working groups was facilitated by CREA and CRPA staff and supported by the use of A0-sized canvases, where the rapporteur was able to take notes summarising the discussion.

The canvas was organized into several sections:

- Description of the most common use systems in Italy.
- Problems of the current system (legislation, air pollution, GHG emissions, assessment of input material as waste or by-product, etc.).
- Description of the compost use system.
- Strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of manure value chain in Italy or in the local context.
- Innovative ideas to solve the weaknesses of value chains (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8: Canvas used to take notes during the discussion in the working group around tables.

3.3.2. **Main outcomes of the focus group on compost**

The barriers of the Italian compost value-chain highlighted in the working groups discussion are summarized in Tab. 8, together with possible solutions and innovations.

Issue	Possible solutions and innovations
Low use of compost and no incentives for compost use.	Efforts should be made to include the agronomic use of compost as one of the practices to generate carbon credits.
Release of odours from compost production.	To promote the use of compost alone or in combination with other organic fertilizers (e.g. manure and compost) in the anaerobic digestion plant.
Poor assessment of ecosystem services from compost.	Provide for the creation of indicators to assess and control the amount of carbon dioxide stored for marketing and carbon credits purposes.
<p>The quality of compost:</p> <p>Presence of plastic in compost: causing a poor recognition of the potential of compost in anaerobic digestion plants and has effects on soil, biome and food chain from the presence of compost of plastic and bioplastic fragments are still unknown.</p> <p>It is noted that the quality of compost differs from lot to lot and plant to plant as it depends on the matrices in inputs (type of waste: urban solids or from the pruning and felling of public greenery) and their proportion.</p>	<p>To promote research aimed at reducing the impurities present in the compost (plastic and bioplastic).</p> <p>Encourage the use of compost in anaerobic digestion plants.</p> <p>To encourage the implementation of research projects investigating the effects of micro/nano plastics and bioplastics in soil and on the food chain and biome.</p> <p>Provide for the definition/application of compost quality protocols which also describe the proportion of waste in inputs and the commodity composition of output produced.</p>
Psychological and cultural limit: the population perceives compost as a dirty material (especially when derived from solid municipal waste) and therefore it is suspicious.	<p>To increase and promote farm advice and training in order to dispel the myths about compost.</p> <p>Provide for the establishment of a quality label for compost.</p>
Unbalanced relationship between the cost of the production plant and the revenues obtained by the operator of the installation. At the moment, it is not profitable to invest in plants able to close the cycles locally or at company level.	Provide economic relief (e.g. reduced taxes – V.A.T.) for users of compost from waste meeting certain standards. Alternatively, the tax burden on chemical fertilisers/soil improvers should be increased.

Tab. 8: Barriers and possible solutions for the Italian compost value-chain.

4. Concrete opportunities emerging from the focus groups

4.1. Biochar

An opportunity available in Italy to respond to request of **incentives** to develop biochar production, was described during the focus group by the Emilia-Romagna region. A representative of the region alerted the participants about a **grant**, which will open soon, in the framework of the Regional Development Programme of the Common Agricultural Policy. The grant is dedicated to biochar production, coupled with energy recovery, and biochar use in agricultural soils. Projects can be granted if the forecasted eligible expenses are among 20.000 and 500.000 €. The aim of the grant is to promote agricultural sustainability, renewable energy production and mitigate climate change in the Emilia-Romagna region.

Regarding the need of promoting knowledge about biochar in Italy, the Italian Biochar Association (ICHAR), which is active since 2009, is promoting two important **dissemination** events:

- May 2024: the Italian school of biochar dedicated to the analysis of threats and opportunities of the Italian biochar value chain;
- October 2024: study tour in Tuscany, organized together with the International Biochar Initiative (IBI), to visit the long-term biochar experimental sites in viticulture, which are the oldest in the world. The main international experts in the field will take part of this study tour giving also lectures on the topic.

Regarding biochar knowledge gaps, CREA produced a short **video** highlighting the very low level of awareness about biochar by farmers, the key actor of the value chain, who are supposed to use it. The video was highly appreciated, and it was broadcasted by the participants to the event to their contacts. Here are the links:

- Italian version: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=I8dVNWIdIUs>
- English version: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hmXb7KPoclo>.

Regarding the need of **small-scale plants**, the KiRa technology farm attended the focus group and described their 1 kWe production and cogeneration unit.

Regarding the need of gathering small farmers in **consortia**, the Frantoio Greve Pesa attended the focus group and described their experience of olive and vine growers' association that collect pruning residues and produce biochar in a consortium gasification plant developed by Yanmar R&D Europe. The local and sustainable value chain attracted a lot of good feedbacks, however the project is still in the testing phase.

The fact that economic sustainability is better achieved when the **condensated co-products** are commercialized, is confirmed by the experience of two companies attending the focus group.

Regarding the need of **training of agronomist and advisors**, a huge action has been put in place in Lombardia, by one of the attendees of the focus group.

The peer-to-peer exchange of experiences could be the key to promote the application of these solutions more widely in Italy.

4.2. Digestate and manure

Among renewable energy sources, anaerobic digestion, is a technology widely used by Italian farms. In 2023, 2.201 biogas plants were operational, of which 1.734 are in agricultural farms (source: CIB, 2023) and, mainly, in the Padano Basin regions.

Anaerobic digestion plants in Italy are fed by more than 40 million tons of processed agricultural biomass:

- around 60% manure,
- around 30% dedicated crops and
- around 10% agro-industrial by-products,

producing about 2,2 billion standard m³ of biomethane and about 3 million tons of digestate (Source: Italian Biogas Consortium, CIB).

Anaerobic digestion has become indispensable for the agricultural company's diversification, because it allows to produce both on-site renewable energy (biogas and biomethane) and natural organic matter (digestate) reducing the use of synthetic chemical fertilizers and emissions of ammonia and GHGs.

It is noted that, also in Europe positive trends are observed in the diffusion of this technology: renewable gases (biogas and biomethane) production is 21 billion m³, representing 6% of the EU's natural gas consumption, and the current biomethane production grew 20% compared to 2022.

Despite the supply chain is well developed since many years, it is noted that in Italy the very regionalized production and distribution of digestate to the agricultural soils causes problems of surplus or shortage of soil organic matter. Therefore, it is important to encourage business advice and training among stakeholders in the anaerobic digestion. In this regard, it is worth mentioning the guidelines produced by CIB for the proper management and use of digestate in organic farming (link: https://www.consorziobiogas.it/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/CIB-Federbio_Linee-guida-uso-agronomico-digestato-in-agricoltura-biologica.pdf).

These guidelines, together with the recent Joint Research Centre (JRC) report on techniques for the safe use of livestock manure even if applied above the threshold laid down for nitrate vulnerable zones by the Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC); can be used as an inspiration for the revision of the regulatory framework about the agronomic use of digestate.

To respond to the need of increased awareness in the field of digestate, and to collect more evidence on the opinion of digestate value-chain actors, mainly farmers, on the use of digestate, interviews were held during the Agricultural Fair (Fieragricola) of Verona, Northern Italy, in February 2024:

- https://youtu.be/d7K1T3f7UGM?si=7-UxtrbyR_RUnVys (video in Italian).

Moreover, to favour innovation in the value chain, CREA has carried out a series of on-site visits to innovative anaerobic digestion plants and the corresponding video were made available on youtube. In detail, we visited:

- the anaerobic digestion plant of Bibbiano, Reggio Emilia province, belonging to the Società Cooperativa Agricola Stalla Sociale Piazzola. The plant has a single-type diet as it is fed exclusively with effluents from dairy cattle (<https://youtu.be/y2feypu7Zpg?si=CzaZJS7s4YhZxp4q>);

- the anaerobic digestion plant of the Innovation Center of Giussago, Pavia province. The plant has a co-digestion diet consisting of a mix of matrices: sewage sludge, civil wastewater, organic fraction of urban waste and manure (<https://youtu.be/RRKB0q1po-U?si=L6BBeeHCb4G86r-5>);
- the consortium anaerobic digestion plant of the municipality of Schiavon, Vicenza province (<https://youtu.be/vaYy1htUjgl?si=T2UaUm6nYPW5TK1L>);
- the anaerobic co-digestion plant located of Assoro, Enna province, in Sicily fed by agro-industrial waste deriving from citrus transformation industry and olive oil mills and from animal waste (e.g., chicken manure and litter). (<https://youtu.be/yiKE018zOis?si=bEQOiWG-uGGyu0YW>)

4.3. Compost

In the agricultural sector, the use of compost as an agricultural soil improver is still little explored. There is potential for the application of compost in the agricultural sector, particularly in the integration between composting and digesters which are transforming masses of agricultural by-products into biogas and digestates. The anaerobic digestion process concerns livestock effluents, plant biomass, animal by-products, as well as the organic fraction of municipal solid waste. An integration of this type certainly represents an opportunity also from an environmental point of view. In terms of composting, in fact, a critical issue has always been that of the spread of odors: with integration with anaerobic digestion, composting takes place in a closed, manned and purified plant.

Compost:

-urban waste and public green areas, corresponding to an annual quantity of approximately 7.3 million tonnes, made up of organic waste (5.5 million tonnes) and greenery (1.8 million tonnes);
-sewage sludge and agro-industry waste, approximately 8.4 million tonnes.

This quantity is transformed into approximately **1.9 million tonnes of compost**, including mixed composted soil improver, green composted soil improver and composted soil improver with sludge, as well as 409 million cubic meters of biogas and 167 million cubic meters of biomethane (CIC, 2024).

The group has highlighted the lack of effective take-off of compost from a commercial point of view. On the one hand, the quality of organic waste collected separately is decreasing, and in reference to this aspect a **quality label** for compost would certainly be appropriate. But the most important reflection to make refers to the reduced appeal that compost has among the farmers (potential user) and therefore to the ways in which this appeal can be improved. Scientific research on composting develops and proceeds, but at the same time there is an evident lack of knowledge on the part of farmers of the qualities of compost and the advantages that its use can generate. In addition, an improvement in the professionalism of both the technicians and the individual plant, i.e. the figure who usually communicates with the farmer, should be actuated. At the same time, rural networks should play an amplification role, encouraging the dissemination of knowledge of the importance of organic matter in the soil and its soil amendment characteristics. The aim should not be to highlight the hypothesis that the use of compost is the solution to the entire problem of desertification (20% of the national territory is at risk of desertification), but to convince that organic substance can contribute significantly to achieving this solution. From the perspective that the land is a community asset. In addition, a lack of communication and penetration of the concept of compost in the agricultural world is an asset. The solutions to this critical issue refer to the development of projects at local and national level to encourage farmer awareness, with repercussions in terms of benefits for the environment. It is necessary to highlight all the advantages for the farmer, both direct and indirect.

The results of the focus groups can be summarized in three strands:

- **Incentives for producers and users of compost:** the agronomic use of compost should be included among agricultural practices that can generate carbon credits. It would also be appropriate to include ad hoc measures in the CAP Strategic Plan in order to stimulate the system. It would be appropriate to provide for economic reductions for those who use compost from waste.

- **Compost quality:** provision should be made for the establishment of a compost quality label. Provide for the definition/application of compost quality protocols which also describe the proportion of waste in inputs and the commodity composition of output produced. To encourage the implementation of research projects investigating the effects of micro/nano plastics and bioplastics in soil and on the food chain and biome.
- **Information on compost:** There is also a need to raise awareness among producers and users of compost.

5. Conclusions

The use and application of EOMs (e.g., animal manures, biochar, digestate, compost, etc..) is increasing worldwide, which can be used as a source of exogenous organic matter for soil. The soil application of EOMs as amendments has been proposed as an effective way of restoring degraded soils, while at the same time, protecting the environment as their use could be part of a strategy to eliminate massive amounts of sub products. This is particularly relevant in the current attempts to reach a fully circular economy, which advocates for capturing and reusing organic wastes.

Among the lessons learned during the focus groups conducted in Italy about organic matters, a first recommendation is the need to economically value the ecosystem services provided by the agro-energy sectors that produce organic matters (compost, digestate, manure and biochar) and renewable energy. They should not only be considered to improve the characteristics of the soil but also as products that can provide benefits in terms of climate mitigation (carbon farming), decarbonization of other sectors and improvement of air quality. This is necessary because the management costs of organic matter (production, storage, application to the soil, etc.) and energy plants (e.g., anaerobic digestion, composting or pyrolysis) are high. At present, the incentives are linked to the construction of the anaerobic digestion plants and the income is exclusively linked to the production of energy placed on the market.

It is also necessary to outline innovative solutions for the use of EOMs (other than agricultural and energy use). Therefore, applied research should be supported regarding e.g., the recovery of biogenic CO₂ from the biogas and biomethane production process, the combination of various organic matters (e.g. digestate and compost/algae/biochar), the production of bioplastic starting from manure thanks to the action of the black soldier fly or the use of biochar in composite materials and batteries.

Finally, in 2023, the first Italian public call for proposals, for the construction of new biomethane plants or for the conversion of biogas plants into biomethane production unit, was launched. In this respect, it is necessary to ensure a rapid connection to the gas network and greater integration between transmission and distribution networks. Finally, even if not subsidized, it is necessary to safeguard the continuation of production activity both for biogas plants that cannot be converted to biomethane and for small-scale plants.

In parallel, the Emilia-Romagna Region, in the north of Italy is launching a call to support the construction of biochar plants, based on a local value chain, in the framework of the Rural Development Programme of the CAP. But this is the first case of public support for pyrolysis and gasification production units. Consortium-level production plants are also seen as a possible way to share the costs and benefits of such complex technologies. Overall, apart from manure, in Italy we observe a general low awareness of the potential benefits deriving from EOMs. A thriving information campaign should be built, especially based on field plants visits.

A fundamental step that emerged from the various focus groups is to define a sort of monetization of the contribution of soil improvers to the soil, not only as an improver of the soil's performance (considering that soil improvement produces concrete and economic effects only in the long term), but from a more immediate perspective, which is of concrete interest for the agricultural company.

In other words, it is necessary to correctly account for the benefits in terms of carbon: direct benefits (those of the different EOM that goes into the ground) and indirect ones, the latter linked for example

to improvements in the environment (the contribution to reducing CO₂ was mentioned). Considering, however, that the CO₂ problem concerns not only agriculture, but all sectors, including industrial and transport, and that it would be appropriate to identify common evaluation parameters.

At the same time, a regulation is needed at the European Union level, with shared rules on the certification of carbon sequestration, on the indicators for controlling the increase in stored CO₂, involving a series of activities including those of carbon farming, with the related carbon credits. It would then be desirable to have a national-level structure that systematically monitors the impact that soil improvers have on the soil. Without forgetting that identifying soil indicators is a rather complex task. A final aspect taken into consideration concerns the logic with which it is appropriate to think about the improvements obtained by the individual farm. It is not up to the farmer to demonstrate that his soil improves with the use of EOMs; but it is more reasonable to focus on the farmer's willingness to follow certain lines of good practices aimed at improving the soil in terms of organic substance. If these practices, validated by the world of research, are followed correctly, then it is appropriate for farmers to obtain an economic reward; in this way, it will be incentivized to continue using EOMs. In other words, **“I reward you for your effort, not based on the result”**.